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NUTRITION:

Is fibre the next big sports supplement?

NUTRITIONIST TIM LAWSON OF SECRET TRAINING LOOKS TO SEE IF SUPPLEMENTING FIBRE CAN IMPROVE YOUR ENDURANCE PERFORMANCE.

INTRODUCTION

When prompted, most people acknowledge that they should probably consume more dietary fibre but wouldn't think it was high on the list of potential ergogenic sports supplements. In fact, the mention of fibre tends to trigger thoughts of 'bland' tasting breakfast cereals that have been around since the early 1900's rather than state of the art sports supplements.

Wheat based high fibre breakfast cereals do have a long history, but came to prominence in the late 1970's and early 80's, after scientists studying different populations found links between low fibre consumption and the incidence of certain diseases. Populations that consumed low amounts

of dietary fibre were found to suffer much higher incidence of colorectal cancers. The flood of scientific publications surrounding these links provided a favourable climate for promoting bran based cereals, even though some questioned equivalence of wheat bran fibre with that used in the epidemiological studies. Wheat bran is mainly insoluble fibre, which is neither digested in the upper gastrointestinal tract nor fermented by bacteria in the lower gastrointestinal tract. Wheat bran and other insoluble fibre absorb water, which increases faecal bulk and reduces gastrointestinal, and colonic transit time.

Modern population studies suggest that Western diets contain as little as 10-15g of dietary fibre per day, this is less than half that recommended as a preventative for many diseases, and tends to be composed of more bulk than soluble fibre. For this reason, increasing fibre consumption

remains a critical public health goal for health promotion and disease prevention in many countries.

Evidence from ancient and primitive civilisations suggests that fibre consumption levels between 60 and 100g (mainly of soluble fibre) may be more representative of paleo diets, therefore optimal amounts may be much higher than the 30g per day recommended for disease prevention.

Speeding gastrointestinal motility may result in more fermentable substrates being delivered to the colon without other dietary changes. This may convey some of the benefits of soluble fibre, though increasing faecal bulk would seem unlikely to improve performance in most sports. In fact, some performance nutritionists have recommended limiting fibre consumption as part of a 'low residue' diet. It is possible to lose up to 1kg or more in the 24 hours before important competitions with this practice. In some circumstances this may be a viable way to improve power to weight ratio and improve performance in sports like cycling and running.

Whilst reducing bulk fibre for short periods prior to important competitions may be a viable way of improving sports performance it may be a mistake to avoid soluble fibre. Specific soluble fibre supplements may be a convenient way of maintaining the benefits of dietary fibre without overly increasing 'residue' in days before competition. Some soluble fibres can also act as nitric oxide modulators in the GI tract and this may confer some protection for the gut against damage caused by NSAID drugs and heat stress.

However, the implications of soluble fibre consumption is much more interesting when they act as prebiotics. In other words, they provide the food for the good bacteria that most people are aware of as prebiotics in yoghurt and

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other fermented milk drinks. In many cases, studies have shown that preferentially feeding the good bacteria, through prebiotic consumption, can have a more prolific effect on the population of beneficial gut bacteria than taking the live bacteria (probiotics) themselves.

Gut bacteria have been shown to produce important nutrients for the host human enabling for instance a calorific value to be derived from non-digestible starch and other sugars that escape digestion in the upper GI tract. Of increasing interest is the production of short chain fatty acids (SCFAs) including propionate, acetate and butyrate. These SCFAs provide fuel directly for the GI tract but can be absorbed through the colon increasing plasma levels. They then act as a source of energy but also as important chemical messengers that

affect fuel utilisation, mood and even satiety.

Depending on the specific fibres (fuels) consumed, and the type of bacteria present in the gut, different combinations of SCFAs can be produced, this is an increasingly interesting area of research. All these SCFAs have a calorific value so it is perhaps surprising that there has been a long held association between fibre consumption and weight loss.

In a 2009 study researchers concluded that for every 1g of fibre consumed per day body weight decreased by 0.25g over a 20-month period. Another study published in the same year suggested that consuming an additional 14g of fibre for two days per week resulted in a weight loss of nearly 2kg in less than four months. More aggressive interventions using specific dietary

fibres have demonstrated significant reductions in body fat and favourable changes in BMI in as little as six weeks.

Fibre consumption may affect body weight by several different mechanisms depending on the type of fibre consumed and this lack of a specific characterised mechanism is proving problematic for those seeking an EU approved health claim in this area. One might expect predominantly bulk fibres to contribute to stomach fullness without adding calories, improving satiety and thus reducing voluntary energy consumption. Indeed, a 2016 study with the mainly bulk fibre psyllium showed that it was effective in controlling hunger between meals.

Paradoxically, SCFAs produced from bacterial fermentation of soluble fibre provide a calorific

value, suggesting alternative mechanisms may be responsible for any weight loss associated with its supplementation.

In 2016 researchers from Imperial College London discovered that one SCFA, propionate, modified eating behaviour by reducing the anticipatory reward response to high energy food. This suggests that if propionate levels are kept high then people are less likely to overeat. These researchers suggested that consumption levels of soluble fibre required to achieve significant levels of propionate may be impractical in Western diets. This has prompted research into the development of a propionate ester supplement that may be taken directly.

Similarly, a ketone ester supplement has been developed to directly increase plasma levels of butyrate, a major SCFA produced by the colonic fermentation of certain soluble fibres and an important major fuel for epithelial cells within the GI tract. The ketone ester supplement has created much hype and controversy in sports circles, promising to revolutionise fuelling for endurance events. What has been described as metabolism's ugly duckling is now thought of as a super fuel that may improve physical and mental performance, improve

body composition and potentially cure many diseases.

Natural ketone production tends to be associated with either starvation or severe carbohydrate restriction whilst the production of ketones via fermentation of soluble fibre has been largely overlooked. Several studies confirm that it is possible to increase plasma levels by supplementing certain soluble fibres, and when butyrate levels are increased this way body composition tends to improve.

In 2015 an animal study shed some light into how butyrate can improve body composition. It was discovered that when plasma butyrate levels were increased fat metabolism was increased via activation of the genes controlling fatty acid oxidation. These researchers obtained similar results either by directly elevating butyrate or stimulation of plasma levels through the supplementation of soluble fibre and probiotics. This may prove to be a simple practical intervention for those athletes wishing to improve their fat burning capacity.

PRACTICAL WAYS TO INCREASE FIBRE CONSUMPTION

Possibly the best way is to increase consumption of fresh vegetables

which is nice in theory but practically challenging to alter diets sufficiently to reach optimal levels. It is also possibly important to recognise that modern fruit and vegetables have been selectively bred over many years to be sweeter and easier to eat and tend to contain less fibre. Most important however is that modern diets often include refined sugars, flours and other carbohydrates devoid of the fibre they would have contained in their natural form. Specific fibre supplements may offer a way to bridge this gap.

Substituting standard porridge oats for varying proportions of oat bran can be a way of both increasing fibre content and reducing the carbohydrate load of what for many is their standard breakfast. Oat fibre contains both bulk fibre and the specific soluble fibre beta-glucan which is also present in barley. When given at dosage greater than 4g per 30g of carbohydrate this soluble fibre has approved EFSA claims for the maintenance of normal blood cholesterol levels and reducing the postprandial glycaemic response. This technique of

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substituting oat bran for oats can help to reduce calories and maintain satiety on non-training, or easy training days when there is less need for a high-energy breakfast.

Specific soluble fibre supplements have been developed that target the production of butyrate ketones in the lower GI where they have the biggest effect on plasma levels (e.g. ellagitannin, secret-training).

Fibre supplementation should always be done gradually since sudden changes are likely to result in gastrointestinal discomfort. Increasing the food available to methane producing bacteria is likely to increase methane gas production for instance, and it may take some time for methane consuming bacteria to respond to the increase. Consumption of probiotics either as supplements or as fermented foods such as live yoghurt, kefir or sauerkraut may also be helpful.

SCIENCE IN PROGRESS

Our understanding of the

human microbiome and how it relates to optimal health is developing rapidly as researchers look deeper into the symbiotic relationship between gut bacteria and the human host. Ensuring that you have healthy bacteria and keep them well fed may have implications far greater than disease prevention, blood glucose control and energy delivery through ketone production. Healthy bacteria have recently been shown to have an important role in delivering some of the health benefits we expect from consuming superfoods

Researchers have long been puzzled as to why the expected health benefits of pomegranates do not extend to all consumers. Recently however, a Swiss research laboratory discovered that it is not the compounds within pomegranates that are directly responsible. Rather, pomegranates provide the raw material for commensal bacteria to produce beneficial compounds.

In technical terms pomegranates contain ellagic acid which is converted to urolithin-A by probiotic bacteria. Urolithin-A is then thought to increase the process of making new fully functioning mitochondria (the energy producing powerhouses of your cells) from damaged ones. If you lack sufficient healthy bacteria to do the conversion, it isn't going to happen.

A LONGTERM PERFORMANCE BOOST

On the surface dietary fibre and probiotics may not seem so exciting but there are plenty of good reasons to think about optimising consumption. There is already mounting evidence that the benefits of soluble fibre go far beyond regularising gut function. Whilst the benefits of consuming more soluble fibre are unlikely to offer the instant hit of a double caffeine gel for instance the longer-term health and performance benefits may be much more significant.

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